

Self-Efficacy as Correlate of Marital Satisfaction of Married Persons in Anambra State.

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Abstract

This study investigated self-efficacy as a correlate of marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra State. The study was guided by relevant research questions and hypotheses tested at the 0.05 level of significance. A correlational research design was adopted. The population comprised 1,469,916 persons who were statutorily married between 2021 and 2023 in Anambra State. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 520 respondents was determined. Stratified random and purposive sampling techniques were used in selecting participants. The General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES) and the Marital Satisfaction Inventory (MSI) were the main instruments for data collection. The instruments were face-validated by experts and yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 for GSES and 0.84 for MSI using Cronbach Alpha. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis. Findings revealed a very low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons. Specifically, there was a very low positive relationship for male married persons and a low positive relationship for female married persons in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended that marriage counselors should promote programs that enhance self-efficacy skills to improve marital satisfaction.

Keywords: Marriage, Self efficacy, Marital Satisfaction

Introduction

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

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Marriage is a formal and legal union between two individuals, typically recognized by law, in which they commit to share their lives together. It is a social institution that signifies a partnership, often based on love, companionship, mutual support, and shared responsibilities. Marriage is a significant institution that serves as the foundation of family structures and societal relationships, providing stability, support, and a framework for personal growth and development within a committed partnership. Okesina (2022) defined marriage as a social institution under which a man and a woman make a decision to live together as husband and wife by legal commitment and religious ceremonies. In his view, Odebunmi (as cited in Anyamene & Etele, 2020) viewed marriage as the union of man and woman as husband and wife, which constitute the basic and essential unit of the society. The author viewed marriage as a contract between two people of opposite sex with the aim of living together, sharing their experiences, making children and raising them. Marriage is recognized as a legal relationship between a male and a female adult, which imposes specific rights and obligation on them. Beyond the private sphere, marriage has significant implications for family stability, child-rearing, and societal cohesion. A successful marital relationship serves as a foundation for emotional and psychological well-being, whereas a dissatisfying marriage may result in emotional distress, health issues, and even divorce (Robles et al., 2016; Amato, 2017). Therefore, exploring the factors that sustain marital satisfaction is essential for enhancing family and societal welfare.

Marital satisfaction is a subjective evaluation by individuals regarding the quality, happiness, and fulfillment they experience in their marriage. Abiodun et al (2022) defined marital satisfaction as the physical, emotional and mental state among couples in which there is an overall feeling of happiness and satisfaction with their marriage. Scholars view it as a multidimensional construct encompassing emotional intimacy, communication, trust, mutual respect, and sexual satisfaction (Fincham & Beach, as cited in Abiodun et al., 2022). High levels of marital satisfaction are often linked with lower levels of stress and depression, greater life satisfaction, and more cohesive family functioning (Etele et al., 2023; Tumin et al., 2015). It encompasses various aspects of a marriage including communication, intimacy, trust, emotional support, sexual satisfaction and overall sense of partnership and support within the marriage. Marital satisfaction is a crucial

component of general well-being and can have influence on both the individuals and the relationship. To maintain and increase marital satisfaction, it is crucial for couples to consistently focus on strengthening their bond, and resolving any problems that may occur. The researcher defined marital satisfaction as the level of fulfillment, happiness, contentment experienced by individual within their marriage. Conversely, marital dissatisfaction has been associated with communication breakdowns, financial stress, lack of intimacy, and overall relational decline (Lares & Lehenbaur, 2019; Balderrama-Durbin et al., 2017).

One psychological factor that has gained scholarly attention in recent years as a determinant of marital quality is self-efficacy. Self-efficacy, as defined by Bandura (as cited in Ojaghu & Narimani, 2019), refers to individuals' beliefs in their capabilities to be organize and execute actions required to manage prospective situations. In marital contexts, self-efficacy translates to confidence in managing relationship dynamics, such as communicating effectively, managing conflict, expressing emotional support, and maintaining intimacy (Marzieh et al., 2016; Umaima & Rupali, 2023). Individuals with high marital self-efficacy are better positioned to respond constructively to relational stressors, persist in problem-solving, and maintain a positive relational outlook, thereby fostering higher marital satisfaction. Conversely, those with low self-efficacy in their marriage may struggle with communication, conflict resolution and maintaining intimacy. They may feel helpless and powerless to improve their relationships and may rely on external forces or blame their partners for problems. This lack of confidence can cause males and females to have feelings of resentment, frustration and dissatisfaction in the relationships.

According to Gallagher and Wilson (2018) gender can relate to marital satisfaction. Buttler (2016) referred to gender as role and responsibilities of men and women that are created in our families, society and cultures. Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities, and expectations that a particular society considers appropriate for men and women. Gender is not the same as biological sex, which is as male or female based on physical characteristics such as reproductive organs, chromosomes among others. Gender is a social construct that varies across cultures, and different social groups. It influences how individuals perceive themselves, how they are perceived by others, and how they interact with the world around them.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 17 April 2025

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15160163](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15160163)

However, gender gap is one of the variable that tends to relate with marital satisfaction of married persons. Research on gender differences in marital satisfaction revealed that males showed more marital satisfaction than females married persons (Rabia & Khalid, 2019). Another study by Uwaoma et al (2016) found that female showed more marital satisfaction than male married persons. While Emery (2019) indicated no gender difference in marital satisfaction among married persons.

Again, several studies support the theoretical correlation between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. Hopper (2021) argued that individuals with high self-efficacy are more confident in navigating emotional complexities and relationship challenges. Hopper (2021) defined self-efficacy as an individual's confidence in his ability to complete a task or achieve a goal. , Kirt (2021) viewed self-efficacy as the belief in one's capabilities to achieve a goal or an outcome Shopkrani et al. (2020) emphasized that self-efficacy in a marriage involves the assurance that one can perform specific relationship-enhancing behaviors based on situational demands. Cherry (2018) noted that individuals with strong self-efficacy tend to exert better control over emotions and behaviors, which enhances mutual understanding in relationships. However, those with low self-efficacy often struggle with expressing needs, managing conflict, and showing empathy, which may result in dissatisfaction and emotional detachment in marriage (Brackett et al., as cited in Samad & Mahmud, 2021).

Despite increasing interest in the psychological predictors of marital satisfaction, a significant research gap exists in studies focused specifically on self-efficacy and its relational outcomes within localized, culturally specific populations. In the Nigerian context, specifically in Anambra State, previous researches have often explored broader factors like emotional intelligence, communication, and financial stability (Anyamene et al., 2021; Abidin et al., 2018), with limited focus on the singular role of self-efficacy. Cultural expectations, traditional gender roles, and evolving social dynamics within Anambra State may uniquely shape how self-efficacy influences marital satisfaction, yet these aspects remain under-researched.

This study, therefore, seeks to bridge this gap by examining self-efficacy as a correlate of marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra State. It aims to determine whether individuals' confidence in managing relationship challenges predicts the degree of satisfaction they experience in their marriages. By focusing on this relationship within a specific cultural and geographical context, the study contributes to the growing body of literature on psychological determinants of marital quality and offers practical implications for marital counseling, family life education, and relationship interventions tailored to the Nigerian setting.

Statement of the Problem

Marital satisfaction is the overall happiness and contentment that people experience in their romantic relationships. It encompasses various aspects of a marriage, including communication, intimacy, trust and emotional support. Despite the challenges and difficulties that couples may face, maintaining marital satisfaction is crucial for the well-being and longevity of a relationship.

However, observation has shown that most married people seem not to really experience marital satisfaction. This could be as a result of poor communication, lack of intimacy, unmet expectations, unresolved conflicts, absence of emotional assistance among others. Lack of marital satisfaction can lead to depression, anxiety, sleep disturbances, decreased intimacy, communication breakdown, unhappiness, and frustration. It can also affect couples physical and mental health and has been linked to increased level of stress. Furthermore, marital dissatisfaction can lead to separation or divorce.

Although previous research efforts have been made to determine factors that contribute to marital satisfaction of married persons, none known to the researcher have explicitly delved into investigating the relationship among self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra state. It was therefore, the need to fill this gap that motivated the researchers to carry out the study on self-efficacy as correlates of marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra state.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra State.
2. ascertain the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra State
2. There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra State.

Research Method

The study adopted a correlational research design. According to Nworgu (2015), a correlational design indicates the direction and magnitude of the relationship between two or more variables. This design was considered appropriate because the aim of the study was to determine the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons. The correlational design allows for the measurement of the strength and direction of relationships between variables in their natural setting. The population was 1,469,916 consisting of married

persons between the age of 25-55 years, who were statutorily married between 2021-2023 in Anambra state still living with their spouses. This information was gotten from the Marriage Registry of Anambra state (2023). The sample of the study comprised 520 (260 males, 260 females) married persons in Anambra state. Taro Yamane was used to draw the sample size. Stratified random and purposive sampling techniques were used to draw the sample. Stratification was based on gender and local government areas. Simple random sampling without replacement was used to draw 10 out of 21 local government areas in the state. Simple random sampling was also employed to draw two towns from the 10 local government areas making a total of 20 towns. Purposive sampling technique was used to draw 26 (13 males and 13 females) married person from each of the town selected. The researcher sampled participants who were between 22-55 years, who were statutorily married and living with their spouses. Purposive sampling technique was employed to draw the sample because the researcher selected participants based on specific criteria that are relevant to the study. Nworgu (2015) posited that in purposive sampling technique, specific elements which satisfy the pre-determined criteria would be selected. Two standardized instruments were used for data collection: General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSES): Originally developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995), the GSES was adapted to suit the marital context. It contains 10 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Not at all true) to 4 (Exactly true). The scale measures the respondent's confidence in their ability to deal with various challenges in their marriage and Marital Satisfaction Inventory (MSI): This instrument, adapted from existing literature, includes 20 items measuring key dimensions of marital satisfaction such as emotional intimacy, communication, shared goals, and mutual respect. Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree).

Content validation of the instruments was carried out by three experts in educational psychology and measurement and evaluation from tertiary institutions in Anambra State. Their feedback was used to revise ambiguous items and ensure cultural and contextual relevance. A pilot test was conducted on 50 married persons outside the study area, and the instruments yielded high reliability coefficients using Cronbach's alpha: 0.86 for the self-efficacy scale and 0.88 for the marital satisfaction scale. The researcher employed the services of trained research assistants in

distributing and collecting the questionnaires. The administration took place in churches, community centers, and social gatherings involving married persons. Respondents were assured of confidentiality and informed consent was obtained. The process lasted four weeks to ensure proper coverage and retrieval of responses. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Specifically, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to test the hypothesis on the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. Statistical analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson's Correlation between Self-efficacy and Marital Satisfaction of Married Persons in Anambra State (N=500)

Variables	Self-efficacy	Marital Satisfaction	Remark
1. Self-efficacy	1.00	0.14	Very Low Positive Relationship
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.14	1.00	

The Pearson's correlation displayed in Table 1 indicates Pearson's r between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction was 0.14. This value shows that there was a very low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra state. This implies that as married persons' self-efficacy increases, their marital satisfaction increases to a low degree.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson’s Correlation between Self-efficacy and Marital Satisfaction of Male and Female Married Persons in Anambra State (N=500)

Variables	Self-efficacy	Marital Satisfaction	Remark
Male (n=248)			
1. Self-efficacy	1.00	0.07	Very Low Positive Relationship
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.07	1.00	
Female (n=252)			
1. Self-efficacy	1.00	0.22	Low Positive Relationship
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.22	1.00	

The results displayed in Table 2 indicates that the correlation between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among male married persons yielded an $r = 0.07$ while that of the female married persons was 0.22. These values indicate that the relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married male persons was very low positive relationship whereas for the females, there exists a low positive relationship

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra State.

Table 3: Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Self-efficacy and Marital Satisfaction of Married Persons in Anambra State (N=500)

Variables	1	2	p-value	Remark
1. Self efficacy	1.00	0.14	.003	Significant
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.14	1.00		

The result displayed in Table 3 indicates that there was a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra State, $r = .14, p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra State.

Table 4: Significance of Pearson’s Correlation between Self-efficacy and Marital Satisfaction of Male and Female Married Persons in Anambra State (N=500)

Variables	Self-efficacy	Marital Satisfaction	p-value	Remark
Male (n=248)				
1. Self-efficacy	1.00	0.07	0.290	Not significant
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.07	1.00		
Female (n=252)				
1. Self-efficacy	1.00	0.22	0.000	Significant
2. Marital Satisfaction	0.22	1.00		

The result displayed in Table 4 shows there was a non-significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among male married persons in Anambra state, $r = 0.07, p > 0.05$. Conversely, there was a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among female married persons in Anambra state, $r = 0.22, p < 0.05$. This suggests that

the null hypothesis was partly supported since the relationship was non-significant among married persons but significant among female married persons.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study as shown in Table 1 revealed that there was a very low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra state. This implies that as married persons' self-efficacy increases, their marital satisfaction increases to a low degree. The result of the corresponding null hypothesis in Table 3 indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons in Anambra state. This is in consonance with the findings of Anyamene et al (2021) who reported a very low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married teachers. The findings also agree with the results of Etele et al (2023), Khorasani et al (2017) and Ezurike et al (2021) whose studies revealed a positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. However, the results contradicts the findings of Therimozhi (2017) whose study revealed a no relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of married persons. The reasons for these findings could be that self-efficacy influences how married persons approach, manage, and sustain their relationships. Self-efficacy enables married persons to effectively navigate the complexities of marriage leading to better communication, conflict resolution, emotional regulation and overall relationship quality. The findings also reported a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. This contradicts with earlier findings of Marzieh et al (2016) which reported a significant negative correlation between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. Furthermore, a study conducted by Pour Fard et al (2016) indicated a significant negative correlation between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction. The reason for this contrast in this finding could be traced to cultural differences as the reviewed studies were western-based. Every culture has it peculiarities so the people within the culture.

The findings of the study presented in Table 2 revealed that there was a very low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male married persons in Anambra state. The results also showed a low positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital

satisfaction of female married persons in Anambra state. The findings indicated that increase in self-efficacy of married persons will likely lead to corresponding increase in marital satisfaction of both male and female married person. However, the magnitude of the relationship differed such that while that of male is very low, that of female is low. This result is surprising because research suggests that male exhibit higher levels of confidence, even in situation where their actual performance does not differ from females. The inflated confidence could have contributed to higher self-efficacy.

The findings of corresponding null hypothesis in Table 4 showed a non-significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male married persons and a significant positive relationship between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of female married persons. This is in disagreement with the findings of Marzieh et al (2016) who found a significant negative correlation between self-efficacy and marital satisfaction of male and female students.

Conclusion

The study investigated self-efficacy as correlates of marital satisfaction among married persons in Anambra state. Based on the findings of the study, the study concluded that there was a positive relationship self efficacy and marital satisfaction of married Persons in Anambra state. The study also concluded that the relationship between self-efficacy on marital satisfaction of male and female married persons in Anambra state was positive.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following are recommended:

1. Marriage counsellors should organize seminars, conferences and workshops that promote the learning of self-efficacy. These session can help married persons to better understand and manage their emotions, as well as those of their partners and build confidence in their ability.
2. Governmental and non-governmental organizations in partnership with the marriage counsellors should organize enlightenment programmes for both females and males

intending to marry and married persons focusing on building self-efficacy of couples for satisfactory marital relations

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